

GreenFORCE

Foster Research Excellence for Green Transition in the Western Balkans

D3.3 - 1st Package of Combine Curricula of Teaching Exchange and Secondments Plan/Dossier

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Table of Contents

List of project partners.....	6
Executive Summary	7
1. Project Overview	8
2. The importance of promoting teaching exchange	9
3. Teaching exchange.....	9
3.1 Teaching staff.....	10
3.2 Teaching exchange programmes	15
3.3 Teaching agendas.....	18
4. Secondments activities and objectives	25
4.3 Why is important to organise secondments in GreenFORCE	25
4.4 Brief presentation of the secondment’s experience in GreenFORCE.....	25
7.3 Secondment exchange Staff.....	26
7.4 Detailed presentation of the secondment’s activities	27
5. Deviations	30
6. Conclusions and future activities	30
Annex 1 – Teaching Exchange Report from CEA to U_Polis (Nikolov)	31
Annex 2 – Teaching Exchange Report from UB-GEF to U_Polis (Jeftić).....	32
Annex 3 – Teaching Exchange Report from UB-GEF to U_Polis (Šećerov).....	33
Annex 4 – Teaching Exchange Report from UB-GEF to U_Polis (Živanović).....	34
Annex 5 – Teaching Exchange Report from POLITO to U_Polis (Lami-Todella)	36
Annex 6 – Teaching Exchange Report from POLITO to U_Polis (Caldarice-Mohabat Doost).....	42
Annex 7 – Teaching Exchange UB-GEF to POLITO - Agenda of the activities.....	50
Annex 8 – Teaching Exchange Report from UB-GEF to POLITO (Jeftić).....	52
Annex 9 – Teaching Exchange Report from UB-GEF to POLITO (Secerov).....	54
Annex 10 – Teaching Exchange Report from UB-GEF to POLITO (Zivanovic).....	56
Annex 11 – Secondments agenda: For coordinating activities between Nordregio – Co-PLAN	58

List of project partners

Number	Role	Short name	Legal name	Country	PIC
1	COO	Co-PLAN	CO-PLAN INSTITUTI PER ZHVILLIMIN EHABIITATIT	AL	941177712
1.1	AE	U_POLIS	UNIVERSITETI POLIS SHPK	AL	954870232
2	BEN	POLITO	POLITECNICO DI TORINO	IT	999977754
3	BEN	NORDREGIO	NORDREGIO	SE	999536792
4	BEN	UB-GEF	UNIVERSITY OF BELGRADE - FACULTY OF GEOGRAPHY	RS	933015744
5	BEN	CEA	CENTER FOR ECONOMIC ANALYSES ASSOCIATION	MK	912445536

Executive Summary

One of the objectives of WP 3 is to “increase the scientific research skills of the WB partners through joint engagement into learning and exchange of research methods and practices” (Grant Agreement, pag. 7). In this regard, the project has organised 10 teaching and 2 secondment exchanges in the period from July 2022 to December 2023 (Figure 1). The activity has involved, either as a host or sending institution, all project partners, as clearly expressed by Task 3.3. In this regard, during the project lifetime, a total of 6 exchange periods will be organised (for a maximum of 3 exchanges per year) as follows:

Year-2023

- March 2023 – researchers from CEA and UB_GEF will be hosted by U-Polis
- May 2023 - researchers from POLITO will be hosted by U-Polis
- November 2023 - researchers from UB_GEF will be hosted by POLITO

Year 2024

- April 2024 – researchers Teaching from CEA & U_Polis will be hosted by UB-GEF
- May 2024 - researchers from POLITO will be hosted by UB-GEF
- November 2024 - researchers from U_Polis will be hosted by POLITO

The *D3.3 - 1st Package of Combinate Curricula of Teaching Exchange and Secondments Plan/Dossier* presents the results of this activity conducted during the year 2023. Moreover, the report illustrates the secondments activity as foreseen in Task 3.1. More specifically, the task focuses on the development and consolidation of horizontal scientific research capacities of the WB partners through training and “on-the-job learning”, in short-term staff exchange, and secondments. To achieve that, the report is organised into six sections. The introduction is followed by a brief project overview (section 1). While Section 2 presents the calendar of the teaching exchange activity, section 3 presents the teaching and expert staff involved and underlines their different background. Section 4 presents the teaching exchange programme by offering more details on the contents and topics of lectures/seminars. After that, Section 5 presents the agendas of each teaching experience and the results. Finally, section 6 offers the secondment experience by following the same logic: staff presentation, exchange topics and agendas. A list of eleven annexes has been attached at the end of the report to provide additional context.

Figure 1 - List of participants in relation to the hosting and sending institutions

1. Project Overview

GreenFORCE aims at fostering excellence in the "Western Balkans' green transition" scientific research and innovation of Co-PLAN (Albania), CEA (North Macedonia), and UB-GEF (Serbia) as a means to enhancing their research profile, strengthening research and management capacities of their staff, and contributing to convergence between Western Balkans (WB) and EU research capacities, as well as to broader policy initiatives for the WB region. To achieve this objective, a twinning partnership of five organisations will work closely to produce territorial knowledge through exploratory research and institutional learning, transferring and exchanging knowledge among partner organisations through applying the knowledge management cycle, engaging in networking for sharing, cross-fertilizing and amplifying knowledge at the societal level. Ultimately, the ambition is to transcend from individual learning to enabling institutional learning, ensuring that scientific research and its management practices become institutionalised within the recipient organisations. GreenFORCE will contribute to the impacts of the destination "Improved access to excellence" by enabling pathways of cooperation, exchange, co-design, and co-creation with academia, civil society and policymakers at the regional level. The five partner organisations are Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development in Albania as the coordinating partner; University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography (UB-GEF) in Serbia and the Center for Economic Analysis Association (CEA) in North Macedonia as the two regional partners; and Nordregio, a pan-Nordic research organisation based in Sweden, together with Politecnico di Torino, Italy (POLITO), as the leading EU research institutions. POLIS University in Albania is the affiliate partner of Co-PLAN.

2. The importance of promoting teaching exchange

One of GreenFORCE's main activities is sharing knowledge and competencies among EU and Western Balkans partners. This activity has important implications and repercussions for the participants' academic and scientific profiles. Whether as part of teaching exchanges or secondments, participants benefit from genuine and inclusive knowledge transfer practices. Generally speaking, knowledge exchange impacts on:

- *Advancement in Academic Profiles* - The knowledge exchange allows participants to enrich their academic profiles. Exposure to diverse perspectives, teaching methodologies, and scientific approaches contributes to a more well-rounded and informed academic background.
- *Professional Development* - Participants can learn about the latest advancements in their field, gain insights into varied research methodologies, and stay abreast of current academic trends.
- *Cultural and Interdisciplinary Insights* - Collaborating with partners from different regions fosters a deeper understanding of diverse cultures and interdisciplinary approaches. This exposure can lead to more holistic and inclusive academic practices.
- *Networking Opportunities* - Participation in knowledge-sharing initiatives creates valuable networking opportunities. Connecting with colleagues from different backgrounds and institutions leads to collaborative research projects, joint publications, and other academic partnerships.
- *Increasing Research Collaboration* - The exchange of competencies often sparks collaborative research initiatives. Researchers from different regions can bring unique perspectives to projects,
- *Internationalization of Education* - Teaching exchange contributes to the internationalisation of education, fostering collaboration and mutual understanding among educators and students worldwide. This aligns with the goal of creating well-prepared global citizens for an interconnected world.

To ensure that the knowledge exchange activities allow participants to achieve personal, professional, and academic objectives, GreenFORCE has organised a variety of exchange activities, as illustrated in the following section.

3. Teaching exchange

As part of the project, GreenFORCE has made sure to offer the exchange of knowledge participation the optimal conditions for benefiting the most from each of the events foreseen. More in detail, this activity has been conducted as follows:

- *Diverse Learning Formats* - activating in-person and online intensive modules caters to diverse learning preferences and accommodates participants with various schedules and locations.
- *Specialised Training* - high-level workshops provide an opportunity for specialised training, allowing participants to delve deep into specific topics or skills relevant to their areas of interest or expertise.
- *Knowledge Dissemination* - delivering public speeches allows for disseminating knowledge to a broader audience, promoting awareness and understanding of critical issues in the academic and professional realms.
- *Interactive Engagement* - participation in targeted seminars and ad hoc roundtables fosters interactive engagement. These forums provide open discussion platforms, idea exchange, and collaborative problem-solving among participants.

All the mentioned activities create networking opportunities within the program participants and with external experts or stakeholders. Networking is crucial for building professional relationships, exploring potential collaborations, and staying connected within the academic community. Offering a mix of activities accommodates participants with different preferences and availability.

3.1 Teaching staff

This section presents in more detail the staff that has contributed and benefited from the teaching exchange activities. More specifically, the participants of the teaching exchange have been:

- Dr. Marjan Nikolov (CEA)
- Prof. Assoc. Marija Jeftic (UB-GEF)
- Prof. Velimir Šećerov (UB-GEF)
- Zora Živanović (UB-GEF)
- Ass. Prof. Ombretta Caldarice (POLITO)
- Dr. Danial Mohabat Doost (POLITO)
- Prof. Isabella Lami (POLITO)
- Ass. Prof. Elena Todella (POLITO)

Following, a brief presentation has been provided for each of them.

Dr. Marjan Nikolov	Partner Institution	Background/area of expertise	Email contact
	Centre of Economic Analysis	Economist	makmar2000@yahoo.com
			Institutional link CEA's TEAM - CEA - Center for Economic Analyses

Marjan is the President of CEA and a global PPP expert with a PhD in measuring the efficiency of decentralisation. He has worked in more than 15 countries in Europe, the Middle East and Africa. His area of expertise covers municipal finance and fiscal decentralisation, public financial management, PPP feasibility studies, fiscal transparency and monitoring and cost-benefit analysis. He has prepared, designed and implemented trainings, research papers and policy-making papers on public financial management and decentralisation and has professional experience in numerous assignments in public finances, decentralisation, macroeconomics. Specific expertise focusing on transitional and development economics, econometrics and statistics, public-private partnership, lecturer/trainer, etc.

Prof. Assoc. Marija Jeftic	Partner Institution	Background/area of expertise	Email contact
	Department for Spatial Planning at the Faculty of Geography, University of Belgrade	Urban Planner	marija.jeftic@gef.bg.ac.rs
			Institutional link: https://gef.bg.ac.rs/en/nastavnik/ph-d-marija-jeftic/

Marija is an Associate Professor at the Department for Spatial Planning at the Faculty of Geography, University of Belgrade (UB-GEF) where she teaches 6 undergraduate subjects, 2 master subjects (Regional processes in spatial planning and GIS analysis in planning and arrangement of space) and 1 PhD subject at the same Department (Instruments of Regional Development Planning). Her scientific and professional specializations are: principles and methods of regionalization, spatial and regional development, regional policy, urban and rural

renewal, spatial analyses and geostatistics (GIS in spatial and regional planning). Alone or with co-authors she published 56 papers, two scientific monographs: *The importance of Belgrade in regional integration of Southeast Europe* and *Functional urban region- instrument of polycentric spatial development in Serbia* and participated in preparation of 10 spatial plans, 6 other spatial planning documents and 3 scientific research projects.

Prof. Velimir Šećerov	Partner Institution	Background/area of expertise	Email contact
	Department for Spatial Planning at the Faculty of Geography, University of Belgrade	Urban Planner	velimir.secerov@gef.bg.ac.rs
			Institutional link https://gef.bg.ac.rs/en/nastavnik/ph-d-velimir-secerov/

Velimir Šećerov, PhD is a Full Professor at the Department for Spatial Planning at the Faculty of Geography, University of Belgrade (UB-GEF) where he teaches 6 undergraduate subjects, 2 master subjects and 1 PhD subject at the same Department. Dean of the Faculty from 2021. Published 111 research and expert papers in domestic and international journals and publications, two scientific monographs, edited 18 books from scientific and expert symposiums and one international journal (*Academia Danubiana*, Vienna, 2010). Was a visiting lecturer at universities in Vienna, Ljubljana, Rijeka and Bratislava, faculties within the University of Belgrade, expert institutions, professional associations and international organizations. Member of the Commission for Licensing Construction Companies, National Commission for Examination of Spatial Plans (2004-2012), in the period 1996-1999 the coordinator of the Commission for Public Examination and Professional Debate of the Serbian Society of Urban Planners. Member of the jury for several urban-planning competitions as the representative of the Faculty or an independent expert. In the course of his career took part in several international projects (ESTIA, Iron Gate, EUROMONTANA, UN HABITAT – SIRP, ERASMUS, UNOPS and so on), several domestic projects, and three times, in the projects of the Ministry of Science, the Faculty representative in Spa-ce.net, a network of European scientific institutions engaged in spatial and urban planning. Took part in the development of more than 38 spatial and urban plans and spatial studies (11 times as the project manager) of all levels (the most significant was the Spatial Plan of the Republic of Serbia 2010 and 2022), nine strategies of spatial development of towns/municipalities, several urban plans and environmental impact analyses. Between 2005 and 2009 the National expert of the UN (UN HABITAT – SIRP Program) and from 2022b on the UNOPS Program. On several occasions the coordinator and president of scientific and organisation boards of international and domestic scientific professional gatherings. Won 8 awards as a member of expert teams at the Urban Planners Exhibition, the Charter of the Serbian Society of Urban Planners.

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Prof. Assoc. Zora Živanović	<i>Partner Institution</i>	<i>Background/area of expertise</i>	<i>Email contact</i>
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Zora is associate professor of Introduction to spatial planning in the Faculty of geography, University of Belgrade. She received her PhD degree from the Faculty of geography, University of Belgrade in 2012 (Role of Medium-sized Cities in Uniform Regional Development of Central Serbia). Her main areas are spatial planning, regional planning, urban and rural geography. Her planning interests are in urban and rural regions as well as research of the spatial integration processes. Zora Živanović has published few monographs and numerous articles in various Serbian and European publications.

Assist. Prof. Ombretta Calderice	<i>Partner Institution</i>	<i>Background/area of expertise</i>	<i>Email contact</i>
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			<i>Institutional link:</i> https://www.polito.it/en/staff?p=ombretta.caldarice

Ombretta, architect and urban planner, is Ph.D. in Spatial Planning and Urban Development (Politecnico di Milano, 2014), Post-doc Research Fellow (Politecnico di Torino, 2015-2019). She is currently Assistant Professor in Urban and Regional Planning at the Interuniversity Department of Regional and Urban Studies and Planning (DIST), Politecnico di Torino. She is a Faculty Affiliate Member of the Responsible Risk Resilience Centre - R3C, Politecnico di Torino. Her research activities focus on the interplay between planning and urban resilience through the lens of planning rules. She has ten years of international experience in research, capacity-building and education on the role (and limits) of planning in complex and adaptive systems, assuming a comparative perspective within Europe with particular attention to identifying and transferring good practices. The main interests of her research tackle the challenge on how to make cities more resilient, dealing with the following topics: (i) theories and practices of urban resilience; (ii) mainstreaming resilience in spatial planning; (iii) urban codes and techniques for resilience; (iv) institutional innovation in spatial planning. She is the co-coordinator of the ERASMUS+ Project with the Witwatersrand University Johannesburg on resilience and climate change. She is the junior coordinator of the Risk Management and Adaptation working group of the international programme RESURBE on Urban Resilience and Climate Change Adaptation. She is a member of the scientific committee of the Intensive Training on Urban Resilience (University of Southern of Denmark). She is a member of the Editorial Board of the Springer Book Series "Resilient Cities. Rethinking Urban Transformation".

<p>Research Assist. Danial Mohabat Doost</p>	<p>Partner Institution</p> <p>Politecnico di Torino, Italy</p>	<p>Background/area of expertise</p> <p>Spatial planning</p>	<p>Email contact</p> <p>danial.mohabat@polito.it</p> <p>Institutional link: https://www.polito.it/en/staff?p=danial.mohabat</p>
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Danial, MSc with honours in “Architecture for the Sustainability Design”, is Ph.D. in “Urban and Regional Development (URD)”, is currently a research assistant in the Responsible Risk Resilience Centre - R3C, an Interdisciplinary Research Centre of Politecnico di Torino focused on urban resilience. His research interests span both Urban Resilience Planning and Spatial Justice. He investigates the reasons behind the inequalities associated with the resilience of communities. The aim is to integrate equity and inclusion as significant targets of international policies such as Agenda 2030, just transition framework, and “Leave no one behind” (LNOB) promise. In addition, he also contributes to exploration and application of different methods for place-based vulnerability measurement as a first step of measuring the resilience of the urban systems. The spatial planning decision-making processes are aided by measuring and mapping resilience, since the adopted methodologies enables us to localise the places where the interventions are required to adapt and/or structurally change the system.

<p>Full Prof. Isabella M. Lami</p>	<p>Partner Institution</p> <p>Politecnico di Torino, Italy</p>	<p>Background/area of expertise</p> <p>Planning evaluation and Project appraisal</p>	<p>Email contact</p> <p>Isabella.lami@polito.it</p> <p>Institutional link: https://www.polito.it/en/staff?p=isabella.lami</p>
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Isabella, graduated with honors in Architecture, is Ph.D in “Real Estate and Urban Planning”, MSc in “Real Estate and Urban Planning”, is Full Professor in Planning Evaluation and Project Appraisal at the Interuniversity Department of Regional and Urban Studies and Planning (DIST), Politecnico di Torino, Italy. She currently teaches “Project appraisal” at the MSc degree in Architecture Construction and City and “Plans and projects appraisal” at the bachelor’s degree in “Territorial, urban planning and landscape-environmental planning”, both at the Politecnico di Torino. She is an expert in urban and territorial transformation assessment procedures, both qualitative and quantitative, with a particular focus on the multi-dimensionality of the aspects involved and the integration of the different phases of the decision-making – design process. In this regard, she has extensive experience in Multi-Criteria Decision Analyses (MCDA), Problem Structuring Methods (PSMs) and decision-making processes in the context of urban and territorial transformations, as well as in the management of

participatory processes. Besides this area, another line of research concerns theoretical reflections and the development of models for the assessment of sustainability in urban areas.

Assist. Prof. Elena Todella

Partner

Institution

Politecnico di
Torino, Italy

**Background/area
of expertise**

Planning
evaluation and
Project appraisal

Email contact

Isabella.lami@polito.it

Institutional link:

<https://www.polito.it/en/staff?p=elena.todella>

Elena, architect and MSc with honors in “Architecture Construction City”, is Ph.D in “Architecture. History and Project”, is Assistant Professor in Planning Evaluation and Project Appraisal at the Interuniversity Department Regional and Urban Studies and Planning (DIST), Politecnico di Torino, Italy. Her research activities concern Problem Structuring Methods and complex urban and architectural transformations, by focusing on both architectural design and decision-making processes. She is also involved in national and international projects related to sustainability evaluation and just green transitions.

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3.2 Teaching exchange programmes

This section summarises the teaching exchange programmes delivered by each of the participants in this activity.

From CEA to U-Polis

Marjan Nikolov proposed a teaching activity entitled **“Introduction to Environmental Economics”**, that covered some aspects on how economic activity and policy affect the environment in which we live. The one-day session relates topics from microeconomics (economic preferences, Coase theorem, Pareto efficiency, social and private costs), regulation (economic instruments), cost benefit analysis (economic valuation, externalities, modelling, economic and financial discount rates). The presentation included a workshop and used many illustrative case studies and examples.

Link - [PowerPoint Presentation \(greenforcetwinning.net\)](https://greenforcetwinning.net)

From UB-GEF to U-Polis and to POLITO

Marija Jeftić proposed two teaching activities on functional regionalization and covered some aspects of the role and significance of cities and urban areas in the spatial development of Serbia:

- **“Functional urban areas (FUA) as the instrument of polycentric spatial development of the Republic of Serbia”**: in the light of making a new Spatial plan of the Republic of Serbia 2021-2035 (SPRS), the current state and prospects of spatial development of the functional urban areas in Serbia are elaborated. With reference to previous SPRS and implementation programs, the importance of FUA in the interregional and intraregional integration of Serbia and its environment are critically considered. How the new plan perceived the position and role of urban areas, for the purpose of rational territorial organization of the Republic of Serbia and what changes enacted to establish a coherent space in the Republic of Serbia, are some of the questions this lecture tries to answer. Link - greenforcetwinning.net/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/FUA_JefticM-in-Polito.pdf
- **“Resilient Belgrade: Spatial Planning in the Light of Climate Change”**: concepts of resilience in spatial planning are explained in general and specifically for the City of Belgrade and its “threshold” of vulnerability, to which it can face the side effects of climate change. The lecture covers topics from Resilience Timeline to Belgrade Regional Context (People and Economy, Culture, Arts and Sciences, Infrastructure, Climate and the Urban Environment, Governance and Budget Management, Designing an Innovative Engagement Process, Primary Shocks and Stresses, Assets and Risks). The concept of urban governance on the level of FUA, along with supporting segments, is proposed as the model for future planning of resistant Belgrade agglomeration. Link - greenforcetwinning.net/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Resilience-Marija-Jeftic.pdf

Velimir Šećerov proposed two teaching activities on city planning in Belgrade:

- **“Public interest and city planning in Serbia. Development of Belgrade on the River Banks”**: accelerated urban development and transformation of their physical structures due to the pressure of new construction, expanding a settlement or changing its former purpose requires meeting the new challenges of controlling and directing such phenomena. The brief historical development of Belgrade, with special features, is presented with an emphasis on the part around the Danube and Sava coasts, the most attractive parts of it and the highest zone interests. Particularly important has been the

period after 2000, when a new generation of plans and long-term strategic documents was established (Regional Spatial Plan of the City of Belgrade, Master Plan of Belgrade, etc.) and where a new project cycle has been developed, especially related to the city core. At very close distances, several capital planning actions have been defined, but some of them have not been implemented yet. (Ada Bridge, Concrete Hall, Marina Dorcol, Port of Belgrade, Ada Huja). Since 2012 the ultimate but controversial project Belgrade Waterfront has been of great interest for local (and national) government. Also, the role of planning documents for the validation of (quasi)public interest is presented in the final section of the presentation. Link - [PPT-BGD-WF-VS-TURIN-2023.pptx \(live.com\)](#)

- **“Novi Beograd (New Belgrade). From grey dormitories to the modern city”**: the turbulent history of the development of the city of Belgrade in the 20th century is particularly interesting and visible on the left banks of its rivers (Danube and Sava). After the First World War and the merging of the northern parts of today's Belgrade, first the planning and then the construction expansion related to these areas began. In the early 60s of the last century, the construction of New Belgrade began, dominantly in the spirit of Corbusier's urban matrices and buildings characteristics of the epoch and social order of that time. A mixture of greenery, a well-designed traffic matrix, high-rise buildings and a large percentage of free surfaces, at the beginning there are dormitories of partially oriented populated social structures. After beginning of the 21st century, this area experienced a transformation, to such an extent that it became today an extremely acceptable place for living, business and other activities. Land unencumbered by disputes from the period of nationalization (after WWII) is attractive for building and a magnet for investments. The price per square meter of an apartment is on par with the most elite parts of the old city, the habits and structure of the population are changing, the most elite events are being organized, and the equipping with modern infrastructure continues. The subject of this lecture is a brief presentation of the transformation of New Belgrade and pointing out the most interesting steps in this process. Link - [PPT-NBG-VS-TURIN-2023.pptx \(live.com\)](#)

Zora Živanović proposed two teaching activities on spatial planning and urban system in Serbia:

- **“Spatial Planning in Serbia: From Yugoslavia to European Integration”**: the lecture aims to present the spatial planning system in Serbia, its basic characteristics, its development path, kinds of spatial plans at each territorial level, the contents of spatial plans and spatial planning procedures. The issue of vertical and horizontal coordination, including territorial cooperation, the existence of monitoring and implementation of plans, the coherence of planned objectives and developments in the area, the degree of representation of theoretical methodology in planning documents, the classification of the country into one of the four European planning systems, as well as other numerous problems and challenges for the future in spatial planning in Serbia are contained in this presentation. Link - [Spatial-Planning-in-Serbia-From-Yugoslavia-to-European-Integration..pdf \(greenforcetwinning.net\)](#)
- **“Urban System in Serbia. The Factor in the Planning of Balanced Regional Development”**: the lecture is about basic characteristics of Serbia's urban system after World War II. Results are presented of analysis and methods common in urban geography, notably the Rank-Size Rule and the Law of the Primate City. After that are given explanations about causes of the previous and current situation in the national settlement network, as a prerequisite for planning the future organization of the settlement network. Polarization is evident in the prominent domination of the capital city in terms of population, and this is a key feature of Serbia's urban system. The current situation is the result of an intensive process of urbanization, but also of the establishment of new administrative boundaries after the disintegration of Yugoslavia. The most suitable model is suggested for Serbia's urban system that could help overcome the extreme population concentration in Belgrade and create a basis for organizing an optimal system of centers. Special attention will pay to Belgrade, as the capital and the largest city in Serbia, in the development of settlements and centres within its administrative area, i.e. the territory administratively named the City of Belgrade. An analysis of demographic trends, including commuting trends, and the

functional and morphological changes in the settlements of the Belgrade region between 1971 and 2011 are presented. Link - greenforcetwinning.net/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Urban-sistem-and-Belgrade.pdf

From POLITO to U-Polis

Ombretta Caldarice and **Danial Mohabat Doost** proposed a teaching module on **“Resilience and Climate Change”**. Today over 50% of the world population lives in urban areas, and cities account for 60-80% of global energy consumption and the same level of greenhouse gases emissions, producing 50% of global waste, consuming 75% of natural resources and producing 80% of global GDP. The 2018 CitiesIPCC Research and Action Agenda outlined that currently cities face critical global challenges, mainly related to environmental changes, social crises, critical infrastructure failures, terrorist attacks, technological accidents, and the recent pandemic. To provide a broad answer to climate change and socio-economic uncertainties, cities worldwide have already started to develop specific mitigation and/or adaptation policies/plans/actions in the perspective of urban resilience. Urban resilience aims to increase the ability of urban systems to respond systemically and dynamically to present and future shocks and stresses related to major global challenges: unsustainable development patterns, rapid and unplanned urbanisation, climate change mitigation, and adaptation. In this scenario, the Green Transition aims to overcome the challenges coming from climate change impacts and environmental threads in European Union. Green Transition could be framed appropriately within the resilience-oriented policies and plans since the main objective of Green Transition regards climate neutrality by 2050. At the same time, resilience-based policies and solutions through adaptation and mitigation strategies tries to reduce the adverse effects of climate change on societies.

Starting from this framework, the teaching activity will provide to the students a broad overview on planning policies and tools regarding resilience, climate change and just and green transition. Additionally, students will work on measuring territorial vulnerabilities as a primary step to operationalizing resilience and to support the definition of strategic actions for the just and green transition.

The teaching activity will expand the participants' knowledge on planning policies and tools, responding to the need for a just and green transition in tackling global threats and focusing on resilience and climate change. The challenge the students will face is integrating resilience in climate change-related strategy and planning actions for supporting the just and green transition in Western Balkans, leveraging the opportunity of worldwide best practices. The students will develop their theoretical knowledge on: (i) the fundamentals of resilience in global challenges science; (ii) urban resilience, climate change, and just and green transition in the international policies; (iii) urban resilience practices with case studies from cities worldwide, including strategic and action plans; (iv) toward measuring urban resilience, supporting adaptation for just and green transition. After these theoretical contributions, the students will work in groups. Each group will select a neighbourhood in Tirana and, based on information and data provided by the instructor(s), will work on measuring territorial vulnerabilities and define strategic actions for the just and green transition. The students will develop basic competencies in resilience theory and practices with reference to just and green transition through (i) preliminary knowledge on measuring territorial vulnerabilities, (ii) analysis of the current and future urban trends and drivers at the local level, (iii) forecast of future resilient scenarios for just and green transition.

Link - [Caldarice & Doost lectures \(greenforcetwinning.net\)](https://greenforcetwinning.net)

Isabella Lami and **Elena Todella** proposed a teaching module on **“Problem Structuring Methods for facing urban uncertainty”**. The course, structured as a workshop, illustrates how the notion of multi-methodology could be an effective means to tackle the complexity of real-world situations where, besides the uncertainties referred to the “ordinary” problems of contemporary cities, there are, in addition, new challenges for future cities. The first are connected to the fact that the project of an architectural/urban transformation has to do with uncertainties connected to the environment, values and decisions. The latter refers to disruptive events around climate change

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and pandemics at local and global scales that are currently under debate in the cities and that represent a type of catastrophic event or are just unknown in their effects. The course proposes the adoption of a multi-methodological framework based on Problem Structuring Methods (PSMs) and supported by Multicriteria Decision Analyses (MCDA) in order to tackle decision problems characterised by high levels of uncertainty and complexity.

In particular, the decision process is structured and supported by using a new software called MuVAM, developed by POLITO from a research idea of Prof. Isabella Lami and DEM Future company. MuVAM (Multi-Values Appraisal Methodology) is a methodological approach that uses software to support decision-making processes related to complex problems. It enables analysis, collaborative discussion, shared solution development, and deliberation with respect to a decision problem through an interface designed to make the complexity of the components involved usable. It contributes to the structuring and representation of decision-making problems through a participatory mode, which can take place both in the present and remotely and possibly asynchronously, to facilitate the final deliberation, which still remains in the purely human sphere. MuVAM consists of a multi-methodology combining the Strategic Choice Approach (SCA) (Friend and Hickling, 2005) and Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) (Saaty, 1980), through an innovative pathway, which allows the two methodologies to be combined into a single, interactive, and customizable flow based on the users and the type of case being analyzed.

The assumption is that it is not always possible to find a single uncontested representation of the problem under consideration and therefore models should be used to inform negotiations about the nature of the problem situation. In the problem representation process, stakeholders can understand and discuss the problem, engage with each other, and work to identify potential improvements. Thus, MuVAM could be used by stakeholder groups in a workshop setting, where stakeholders can share and understand different perspectives, to arrive at shared solutions. Unlike all existing and currently applied technologies, MuVAM is based on cloud-based technologies, which allow for synchronized and connected use, without risk of data loss, anywhere in the world, surpassing the limitations imposed by use hitherto necessarily done in co-presence and/or through the use of paper media.

Link - [LamiTodella_Teaching-UPolis.pdf \(greenforcetwinning.net\)](#)

3.3 Teaching agendas

This section summarises the agendas of each teaching exchange experience by detailing each activity conducted.

Exchange from CEA to U-Polis

The exchange from CEA to U-Polis was organized for the second semester of the 2022-2023 academic year – March 2023. According to the agreement between the two institutions, the CEA teaching team included **Marjan Nikolov**.

The teaching activity of **Marjan Nikolov** was coordinated with zoom meetings and tete-a-tete meetings in Tirana in POLIS University premises on 27th and 28th of March 2023. It was agreed that the students of the IDAUP Program, XXXV Cycle are interested to participate on a lecture related to environmental economics. The lecture was carefully designed and structured to also fit the lectures of the colleagues from the UBGEF with whom CEA coordinated joined module for lecturing at the POLIS University. The format of the lecture of the 29th of March was public-open lecture with a duration of 60 minutes together with discussion and questions with the audience at the end of the lecture.

UB_GEF to U-Polis

The teaching exchange from UB_GEF to U_POLIS was organized for the second semester of the 2022-2023 academic year – March 2023. According to the agreement between the two institutions, the UB_GEF teaching team included **Marija Jeftić, Velimir Šećerov, Zora Zivanovic**.

The teaching activity of **Marija Jeftić** was organized in the framework of a combined guest lecture that U-Polis conducted within the project, on the 29th of March 2023, for the students of the IDAUP Program. The lecture was carefully designed and structured to also fit the lectures of the colleague from CEA and other colleagues from the UB- GEF with whom UB-GEF coordinated joined module for lecturing at the U-Polis. The format of the lecture was public open lecture with a duration of 60 minutes together with discussion and questions with the audience at the end of the lecture. The speaker introduced the students to functional regionalization, and elaborated on the topics: model of FUA, spatial planning instruments, Current Strategies, Plans and Development Frameworks.

The teaching activity of **Velimir Šećerov** was coordinated with zoom meetings and tete-a-tete meetings in Tirana in POLIS University premises on 27th and 28th of March 2023. It was agreed that the students of the IDAUP Program, XXXV Cycle were interested to participate on a lecture related to spatial planning. The lecture was carefully designed and structured to also fit the lectures of the other colleagues from the UBGEF and CEA coordinated joined module for lecturing at the POLIS University. The format of the lecture of the 29th of March 2023 was public-open lecture with a duration of 45 minutes together with discussion and questions with the audience at the end of the lecture.

The teaching activity of **Zora Živanović** was organised in the framework of a combined guest lecture that U-Polis conducted within the project on the 29th of March 2023 for the students of the IDAUP Program. The format of the lecture was public open lecture with a duration of 90 minutes together with discussion and questions. The speaker introduced the students to spatial planning and the urban system in Serbia.

From POLITO to U. POLIS

The teaching exchange from POLITO to U_POLIS was organized for the second semester of the 2022-2023 academic year – May 2023. According to the agreement between the two institutions, the POLITO Teaching Team includes **Ombretta Caldarice, Danial Mohabat Doost, Isabella M. Lami, Elena Todella**.

The teaching module of **Ombretta Caldarice** and **Danial Mohabat Doost** was organized from the 22nd to 26th of May, for the students of the bachelor's degree in Environmental Studies, at the Department of Environment, Faculty of Planning, Environment and Urban Management. The teaching exchange on "Resilience and Climate Change" aimed to give the students a comprehensive framework about the EU Green Transition, understating how resilience-oriented policies can have a leading role in overcoming climate change and environmental degradation, fostering climate neutrality by 2050, boosting the economy through green technology, creating sustainable industry and transport, and cutting pollution. The teaching exchange has been organised in five lectures (Table 1) on resilience, climate change, and just green transition in international science, policy and practice, and a workshop on measuring territorial vulnerabilities to supporting just green transition in Tirana. The details of the lectures are reported in the Annex 6.

Generally, the learning outcomes have been the following:

- Develop knowledge of resilience;
- Expand awareness on policies and tools that support a just green transition in tackling global threats;
- Investigate urban resilience practices with case studies from cities worldwide;
- Conduct a preliminary measurement of territorial vulnerabilities in Tirana Prefecture;
- Analyse the current and future urban trends at the local level;
- Forecast future resilient scenarios for just green transition.

Table 1 – Caldarice and Doost’s teaching agenda

Day	Lecture/Exercise	Teacher(s)	h.
1	Lecture 1 – The fundamentals of resilience in global challenges science	Caldarice	2 h
	Lecture 2 – Urban resilience, climate change, and just and green transition in the international policies	Caldarice	2 h
2	Lecture 3 – Urban resilience practices with case studies from cities worldwide	Caldarice	3 h
	Lecture 4 – Preliminary knowledge on measuring territorial vulnerabilities for just green transition	Caldarice	3 h
3	Lecture 5 – The Geographic Information Systems (GIS) in resilience measurement	Mohabat Doost	2 h
	Exercise 1 – Group activities. Stakeholders’ participation for weighting vulnerability indicators	Mohabat Doost	2 h
4	Exercise 2 – Group activities. Analysis of the urban trends and drivers at the local level	Mohabat Doost	2 h
	Exercise 3 – Group activities. Forecast of future resilient scenarios for just green transition	Mohabat Doost	2 h
5	Exercise 4 – Group presentation. From territorial vulnerabilities to just and green transition	Caldarice Mohabat Doost	2 h
Total			20 h

Problem Structuring Methods for facing urban uncertainty

The teaching module of **Isabella M. Lami** and **Elena Todella** was organized from the 15th to 19th of May, for the students of the “Master of Science in Urban Planning and Management” (2nd and 3rd year) and “Environmental Studies” (3rd year), at the Department of Urban Planning and Management. The teaching exchange on “Problem Structuring Methods for facing urban uncertainty” related to methodologies for analysing the feasibility of projects and plans and evaluating their economic and extra-economic effects through monetary or approaches, such as Problem Structuring Methods and Multi-Criteria Decision Analyses. The teaching exchange has been organised in a workshop of lectures and exercises (Table 2).

Table 2 – Lami and Todella’s teaching agenda

Day	Lecture/Exercise	Teacher(s)	h.
1	Introduction and presentation of the GreenFORCE project, the course and the agenda	Lami Todella	30 min
	Theoretical illustration of the multi-methodology (1): the Strategic Choice Approach (SCA) and Problem Structuring Methods (PSMs)	Lami	1 h 15 min
	Indication about the case study and the decision problem	Todella	30 min
	Break	-	15 min
	Brief self-presentation by students and group definition	Lami, Todella	30 min
	Analysis of the case study and initial identification of the decision-making problem (group activity, part 1, with teaching support in classroom if needed)	Lami Todella	2 h
2	Analysis of the case study and initial identification of the decision-making problem (group activity, part 2, with teaching support through google classroom if needed)	Lami Todella	9 h
3	Group discussion and presentation about the identified decision-making problem (group activity)	Lami Todella	1 h 30 min

	Theoretical illustration of the multi-methodology (2): the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Multi-Criteria Decision Analyses (MCDA)	Lami	1 h 15 min
	Break	-	15 min
	Illustration of the MuVAM software and questions	Lami Todella	1 h
	Lunch break	-	1 h 30 min
	Definition of the decision areas from the list and focus (group activity)	Lami Todella	1 h 30 min
	Discussion around the decision areas and focus (group activity)	Lami Todella	45 min
	Identification of the options for the case study (group activity)	Lami Todella	1 h 15 min
4	Definition of the option tree (group activity)	Lami Todella	1 h 30 min
	Discussion on the option tree (group activity)	Lami Todella	45 min
	Break	-	15 min
	Illustration of the KPIs for comparing the alternatives	Lami Todella	30 min
	Comparison with the selection of KPIs provided by us (group activity + individual activity)	Lami Todella	1 h
	Lunch break	Lami Todella	1 h 30 min
	Discussion on the comparisons and results (group activity)	Lami Todella	1 h
	Evaluation of the experience and feedback through a Google form survey	Lami Todella	30 min
Total			30 h

From UB_GEF to POLITO

The teaching exchange from UB_GEF to POLITO was organized for the first semester of the 2023-2024 academic year – November 2023. According to the agreement between the two institutions, the UB_GEF teaching team included **Marija Jeftić, Velimir Šećerov, Zora Zivanovic**.

The teaching activity of **Marija Jeftić** was provided in the module “Economic feasibility of plans and projects” (resp. Prof. Isabella M. Lami), with bachelor’s students in Spatial, Urban and Landscape Planning. The course provides students with a knowledge of the methods of investigation relating to the needs of users and the limits imposed by economic factors for the development of sustainable and feasible architectural projects. At the end of the course the student will have developed the ability to identify the key elements of the real estate market in order to develop a quality architectural project able to respond to the challenges of today's society. The lecture related on “Resilient Belgrade: Spatial Planning in the Light of Climate Change” and provided students with concept of resilience in spatial planning, in general and specifically for the City of Belgrade. The lecture was carefully designed and structured to also fit the lectures of the other colleagues from UB-GEF. The speaker – prof. Marija Jeftić, introduced the students to resilient Belgrade and functional regionalization, and elaborated on the topics: resilience, The City Resilience Framework, Belgrade Strategy of Urban Resilience, model of FUA, spatial planning instruments, Current Strategies, Plans and Development Frameworks.

The teaching activity of **Velimir Šećerov** was provided in the introductory seminar “Resilience and Cultural Heritage” (resp. Prof. Ombretta Caldarice, Prof. Benedetta Giudice; Prof. Michela Benente). The seminar (Table 3)

is part of the Master's degree programmes in Architecture of the Politecnico di Torino. It supports students in dealing with emerging issues related to the resilience of cultural heritage and acquiring specific skills to design resilience strategies. Based on the debate with the local actors, the seminar assumes a territorial perspective to envisage future scenarios and to define strengths and weaknesses to enhance the resilience of cultural heritage. Prof. Ombretta Caldarice introduced the seminar, then Prof. Šećerov provided the lectures "Novi Beograd (New Belgrade) - From Grey Dormitories to the Modern City", and "Public Interest and City Planning in Serbia - Development of Belgrade on the River Banks", on the turbulent history of the development of the city of Belgrade in the 20th century, particularly interesting and visible on the left banks of its rivers (Danube and Sava), and a reflection on accelerated urban development and transformation of Belgrade physical structures due to the pressure of new construction. The discussants of the seminar were Prof. Francesca Bragaglia, Prof. Benedetta Giudice; Prof. Michela Benente and Prof. Irene Ruiz Bazan.

Table 3 - Seminar Programme

Lecture	Teacher(s)	h.
Introduction to the seminar	Caldarice	30 min
Novi Beograd (New Belgrade) - From Grey Dormitories to the Modern City	Šećerov	1,5 h
Public Interest and City Planning in Serbia - Development of Belgrade on the River Banks	Šećerov	1,5 h
Discussion	Bragaglia, Giudice, Benente, Ruiz Bazan	30 min

The teaching activity of **Zora Živanović** was provided within the module "Planning theory and comparative planning studies" (resp. Prof. Giancarlo Cotella). The course provides students of the Master's degree in Planning for the Global Urban Agenda with (i) a theoretical standpoint on the nature of spatial governance and planning systems and how they change and evolve through time; (ii) a critical comparison of selected spatial governance and planning systems in Europe and beyond and (iii) an informed perspective of the institutional and operational influence of transnational organizations over domestic contexts, with particular attention for the European Union. The lecture related "Spatial Planning in Serbia: From Yugoslavia to European Integration", with the aim to present the spatial planning system in Serbia, its basic characteristics, its development path, kinds of spatial plans at each territorial level, the contents of spatial plans and spatial planning procedures.

The visiting teaching exchange continued with a public seminar on "Functional Areas and Urban/regional development: what nexus", that delved into the significance of functional areas in addressing the myriad challenges that territories have encountered over the past three decades (Figure 2). While not a new concept, functional area is indeed increasingly gaining prominence as an approach to define new spatial configurations and territorial alliances based on functional factors, including economic, social, and institutional interrelations. The seminar (Table 4) was introduced by Prof. Erblin Berisha, with a presentation on "Functional Areas: what do they stand for?". Then, Prof. Marija Jeftić provided a lecture on "Functional urban areas (FUA) as the instrument of polycentric spatial development of the Republic of Serbia" on the importance of FUA in the interregional and intraregional integration of Serbia and its environment. Also, Prof. Zora Živanović presented a contribution entitled "Urban System in Serbia. The Factor in the Planning of Balanced Regional Development", about basic characteristics of Serbia's urban system after World War II, and the results of the Rank-Size Rule and the Law of the Primate City analysis on the case study. The discussants of the seminar were Prof. Giancarlo Cotella, Prof. Loris Servillo.

Table 4 - Functional Areas International Seminar

Lecture	Presenters	h.
Functional Areas: what do they stand for?	Berisha	15 min
functional urban areas (FUA) as the instrument of polycentric spatial development of the Republic of Serbia	Jeftić	45 min
Urban System in Serbia—The Factor in the Planning of Balanced Regional Development	Živanović	45 min
Discussion	Cotella Servillo	15 min

Figure 2 - Public Seminar on Functional Areas and the Serbian experiences

Finally, an institutional twinning meeting (2 hours) was organised, Representatives from the DIST-POLITO and UB-GEF at the OGR under the coordination of R3C (Figure 3). The meeting discussed the structure of each institution, shared details about their main research projects, and explored potential areas of research interest and cooperation initiatives in relation to internationalisation and EU projects together with Magda Bolzoni (Referent for Internationalisation), Elisabetta Vitale Brovarone (Referent for Research).

Figure 3 - Institutional meeting on research and internationalisation activities among representatives of POLITO and UB-GEF

4 Secondments activities and objectives

As reported in the Grant Agreement, secondments play an important role in knowledge exchange among GreenFORCE partners. Accordingly, at least 1 researcher from the WB partners will spend 2-3 weeks at Nordregio. The secondments will boost interaction between the host and guest researchers and in bi-directional capacity-building efforts. Issues to address are: 1) management of institutional knowledge repositories and knowledge management tools; 2) processing and analysing of big geospatial data using state-of-the-art spatial data science techniques; 3) production of professional, evidence-based dissemination and communication outcomes; 4) set-up, management and administration of research projects and research management units; 5) accessing outlets for publication of scientific research, including quality writing and complying with publisher requirements. The researchers in this task will apply the knowledge into i) research products of WP4, ii) own organisational processes related to just green transition, iii) the drafting and adoption of a GreenFORCE Scientific Publication Plan to implement beyond the project end.

4.1 Why is important to organise secondments in GreenFORCE

Conducting secondments among partners is important for several reasons as following:

- *Skill Transfer and Development* - Secondments allow experts to share and acquire new skills. Individuals learn from the expertise of their colleagues in the host institution (i.e. Nordregio), contributing to their professional development.
- *Knowledge Exchange* – Experts on secondment bring fresh perspectives and insights from their home institution (i.e. Ub-GEF, CEA and Co-Plan), fostering knowledge exchange between organisations. This cross-pollination of ideas leads to innovation and improved business practices.
- *Enhanced Collaboration* - secondments encourage collaboration between companies. Experts working temporarily in another organisation develop stronger working relationships, which can facilitate future collaboration, partnerships, or joint projects.
- *Succession Planning* - secondments are a strategic component of succession planning. They offer experts involved the *chance* to gain experience in different roles and departments.
- *Flexibility and Adaptability* - exposure to different work environments during a secondment enhances employees' adaptability and flexibility.

Besides that, secondments contribute to enhancing the general quality of expertise in the Western Balkans by transferring knowledge from more experienced partners to others. The experience shows, however, that more experienced partners have benefited from conducting secondments and gaining more knowledge, and the Western Balkans have explored different cultural and knowledge understandings of the same issue (i.e., Just Green Transitions).

4.2 Brief presentation of the secondment's experience in GreenFORCE

The secondment brought together partners from Co-PLAN and CEA together with Nordregio with a mix of objectives, including training (unidirectional knowledge transfer), co-learning (multi-directional knowledge transfer), and addressing project deliverables more practically (by generating a common understanding of

upcoming activities and project deliverables). The activities planned contributed to the deliverables of several of the project's work packages and tasks.

The secondment was planned smartly to make the most efficient way of travel resources. Specifically, by combining the secondment with CEA's teaching exchange (T3.3), a PMB meeting, and the RAB meeting (these activities are reported separately).

4.3 Secondment exchange Staff

<p>Dr. Marjan Nikolov</p>	<p>Partner Institution</p> <p>Centre of Economic Analysis</p>	<p>Background/area of expertise</p> <p>Economist</p>	<p>Email contact</p> <p>makmar2000@yahoo.com</p> <p>Institutional link</p> <p>CEA's TEAM - CEA - Center for Economic Analyses</p>
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Marjan is the President of CEA and a global PPP expert with a PhD in measuring the efficiency of decentralisation. He has worked in more than 15 countries in Europe, the Middle East and Africa. His area of expertise covers municipal finance and fiscal decentralisation, public financial management, PPP feasibility studies, fiscal transparency and monitoring and cost-benefit analysis. He has prepared, designed and implemented trainings, research papers and policy-making papers on public financial management and decentralisation and has professional experience in numerous assignments in public finances, decentralisation, macroeconomics. Specific expertise focusing on transitional and development economics, econometrics and statistics, public-private partnership, lecturer/trainer, etc.

<p>Msc. Alberto Giacometti</p>	<p>Partner Institution</p> <p>Nordregio</p>	<p>Background/area of expertise</p> <p>Geographer</p>	<p>Email contact</p> <p>alberto.giacometti@nordregio.org</p> <p>Institutional link</p> <p>Alberto Giacometti Nordregio</p>
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Alberto Giacometti is a Senior Research Advisor at Nordregio. He has a background in human geography, regional development, and planning policy. His current fields of research cover regional innovation systems, multi-level governance, just green transitions, resilience, and circular economy. Alberto has led a number of international projects within the Nordic countries, across the Baltic Sea region, and is involved in others in Balkan and other European regions. To a limited extent, Alberto is also involved in lecturing mostly as a visiting lecturer.

4.4 Detailed presentation of the secondment's activities

This section presents in more detail the activities conducted during the combined secondments of Nordregio and CEA hosted by Co-Plan in Tirana, Albania. It offers an overview of the types of activities and the outcomes, illustrating the heterogeneity of topics, modalities of engagement, and knowledge exchange adopted.

Activity 1 - Discussion on the Policy Briefs (T2.4), topics and focus

This meeting aimed at advancing the work planned for T2.4, which consists of both expanding the capacities of partner organisations on how to formulate policy-relevant documents as well as the application of this knowledge in the writing of 5 policy briefs in total (D2.4 & D2.5). The fruitful discussion focuses both on the format and topics. A decision was made of the topics of the first 2 policy briefs (D2.4), one focusing on the broader concept of the 'Just Green Transition' and contextualisation to the Western Balkans (extracting from D4.1), and the second on the potential of waste-to-energy (based on WP4 case studies and previous research at Co-PLAN). The selection of topics was also made thinking of involving different staff members of Co-PLAN. Thus, the authors involved are different in the two policy briefs.

Activity 2 - Brainstorming and discussion on potential proposals (T2.2)

This session consisted in discussing the proposals partners would be willing to submit based on thematic relevance, interest, and internal capacities (In line with Task 2.2). Limitations identified early in the project however, reduced the type of project partners can join forces (all together) given the specific requirements of funding bodies (ether only EU members, or only Balkan, or only one EU, etc). Yet, Horizon programme was identified as an interesting programme for all (yet a challenging one, due to magnitude and competitiveness), and other small ones such as from the Swedish Institute, SIDA, World Bank programmes. Partners agreed that the main areas of interest are geography, green transitions, and governance.

Activity 3 – Participation and contribution at the National Forum on Climate Change in Albania (within GreenAL project)

With the ambition of extending the participation of GreenFORCE in the broader policy, academic and societal debates on green transition and governance, partners from Nordregio and CEA were invited to participate at the "National Forum on Climate Change in Albania" The 2nd national forum of a series of 5. The event attracted over 100 participants from NGOs, policy, international organisations, embassies, media and academia. It was organized by Co-PLAN in the frame of the Green_AL project supported by SIDA (Sweden's government agency for development cooperation). This activity also contributes to the implementation of T2.4 which states that partners should "participate in at least 2 projects of 'research influencing policy' at Co-PLAN and/or CEA". Nordregio was asked to deliver a presentation unwrapping the concept of the 'Just Green Transition' in policy and academia and urge the civil society participants to take ownership of the concept and adept it to their local contexts.

Activity 4 – Moderate and facilitate a training session with researchers Co-PLAN on how to bridge research - policy (Alberto as lead; Marjan as discussant)

Nordregio led a training session with Co-PLAN young researchers and CEA was invited as discussant. This seminar and workshop was thought as a complementary action to the similar one carried during the PMB meeting in Skopje (and online) in January 2023 (T2.4), but focusing on the general staff of Co-PLAN. Starting from the basics, Nordregio addressed questions such as 'what is policy?', 'who develops and who implements policies?', and so on. Then we mapped out different types of policy areas relevant to the work of all participants present and discussed the diversity of policies, strategies, policy documents and tools that exist in each of them. Examples were given of policy processes carried out in Nordic countries to hint where, when, and how can stakeholders influence policy

decision making processes. Finally, the workshop concluded with tips and tricks on how to write policy briefs – from considering target groups, language, to format and style, as well as how to write actionable policy recommendations.

Activity 5 – Work on Policy Brief No.1 - structure and input (T2.4)

Delivering on task 2.4., the workshop consisted on extracting the key findings of the Just Green Transition (JGT) conceptualisation paper (WP4) by asking ourselves 1) What is our unique contribution (is not already said out there)? 2) What is specific about applying the JGT in the WBs (compared to other countries e.g., EU)? 3) what is the policy relevance (messages that are of use to policy-makers)? The workshop was particularly useful in helping the lead authors (i.e., Fiona and Anila) distance themselves from the academic approach to JGT and reflect on how to formulate ideas that are attractive to a broader audience, as well as to find the 'spicier' issues to catch policy attention. A decision was made to angle the policy brief to focus on the potential of, a so-called, 'transition fatigue' in impeding the design of serious measures, and how to overcome hopelessness with place-based and realistic steps forward. This constituted a first step in a long and productive process of writing and re-writing the main text of the policy brief, sharing ideas across all partners and then formulating actionable policy recommendations.

Activity 6 – Discussion and brainstorming on Macro-regional Networks

The idea with this discussion was to brainstorm on how to deliver on task 2.3 which aims at supporting WB partners in using quality research actively in pushing forward policy agendas and formulating a proposal for regional partnership (D2.3). The discussion proved very useful in generating a common understanding about the challenges and opportunities of existing platforms and in making decisions on how to focus the project's efforts to achieve most impact. Partners acknowledged that the existing platforms, both RCC and NALAS are generally gathering high level officials and to a lesser extend researchers, technical staff from public administrations and the civil society, not only leaving open a wide democratic gap but also limiting the possibility for in-depth and objective discussions on more technical issues. For this reason, partners considered appropriate to focus the development a 'road-map for macro-regional governance' on bottom-up networks (such as TG-WEB) to establish bridges with the more political networks – and as a channel to deliver evidence-based input to decision-makers.

To these activities have been participating the following Co-Plan Staff:

Dritan Shutina, Anila Beiko, Kejt Dhrami, Fiona Imami, Rodion Gjoka, Merita Toska, Aida Ciro, Ogerta Gjikhuri, Elvis Ndreka, Erni Kocani, Rea Muka, Enkela Poro, Besmir Geziqi, Rudina Pasholli, Imeldi Sokoli, Sara Korreshi, Elona Karafili.

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5 Deviations

Even though the project has managed several teaching and secondment exchanges, there have been no significant deviations. The activities have been performed pretty much as planned. However, the only deviation concerns the implementation of the “Resilience and Climate Change” teaching activity organised by POLITO (Prof. Ombretta Caldarice and Dr. Danial Mohabat Doost).

Initially, the activity was planned in person; however, due to some administrative/legal issues, Dr. Danial Mohabat Doost was not allowed to travel to Tirana (AL). Considering the integrated nature of the module, the partners involved (i.e., POLITO and U_POLIS) decided jointly to move this activity entirely online. This deviation has been agreed upon with the Project Officer.

6 Conclusions and future activities

The implementation of the teaching and secondment exchange has been highly appreciated by the participants, who emphasised the importance of sharing knowledge among partners and visiting different institutions. The most appreciated activities are those that involve direct interaction (interactive knowledge exchange) of hosted experts with local representatives and students.

For the upcoming year, the teaching and secondment exchange will involve a number of academics and experts from all project partners. Specifically, in May 2024, teachers from POLITO will be hosted by UB-GEF, further enhancing the existing cooperation between these two institutions. The same will be done by U-POLIS teachers who POLITO will host during the academic activities of October/November 2024.

Similarly, Nordregio will host the secondments representatives of UB-GEF, Co-Plan and CEA.

Annex 1 – Teaching Exchange Report from CEA to U_Polis (Nikolov)

Teaching period – March 27th to 31st, 2023

Visiting researcher: Marjan Nikolov

Sending institution: Center for economic analyses-CEA

E-mail: makmar2000@yahoo.com

Hosting institution

Name: POLIS University

Department: IDAUP Program, XXXV Cycle. Polis University

Contact person: Doriana Musaj, deputy Dean of the Faculty of Urban Planning and Urban Management

Synthesis of the visiting activities conducted (teaching modules/workshops/public-open lectures):

The teaching module was coordinated with zoom meetings and tete-a-tete meetings in Tirana in POLIS University premises on 27th and 28th of March 2023. It was agreed that the students of the IDAUP Program, XXXV Cycle are interested to participate on a lecture related to environmental economics. The lecture was carefully designed and structured to also fit the lectures of the colleagues from the UBGEF with whom CEA coordinated joined module for lecturing at the POLIS University. The format of the lecture was public-open with a duration of 60 minutes together with discussion and questions with the audience at the end of the lecture.

Title: Introduction to environmental economics

Abstract: Environmental economics teaching activities will cover some aspects on how economic activity and policy affect the environment in which we live. This one-day session in *Environmental Economics* will cover topics from microeconomics (economic preferences, Coase theorem, Pareto efficiency, social and private costs), regulation (economic instruments), cost benefit analysis (economic valuation, externalities, modelling, economic and financial discount rates). We will use many illustrative case studies and examples.

Annex 2 – Teaching Exchange Report from UB-GEF to U_Polis (Jeftić)

Teaching period – March 27th to 31st, 2023

Visiting researcher: Marija Jeftić

Sending institution: University of Belgrade, Faculty of Geography

E-mail: marija.jeftic@gef.bg.ac.rs

Hosting institution

Name: POLIS University

Department: IDAUP Program, XXXV Cycle. Polis University

Contact person: Doriana Musaj, deputy Dean of the Faculty of Urban Planning and Urban Management

Synthesis of the visiting activities conducted (teaching modules/workshops/public-open lectures..):

The Polis University conducted a combined guest lecture within Horizon frame, on 29th of March 2023, for the students of the IDAUP Program. The lecture was carefully designed and structured to also fit the lectures of the colleague from CEA and other other colleagues from the UB- GEF with whom UB-GEF coordinated joined module for lecturing at the POLIS University. The format of the lecture was public open lecture with a duration of 60 minutes together with discussion and questions with the audience at the end of the lecture. The speaker – prof. Marija Jeftić, introduced the students to functional regionalization, and elaborated on the topics: model of FUA, spatial planning instruments, Current Strategies, Plans and Development Frameworks.

Title: Functional urban areas (FUA) as the instrument of polycentric spatial development of the Republic of Serbia

Abstract: In the light of making a new Spatial plan of the Republic of Serbia 2021-2035 (SPRS), the current state and prospects of spatial development of the functional urban areas in Serbia were elaborated. With reference to previous SPRS and implementation programs, the importance of FUA in the interregional and intraregional integration of Serbia and its environment was critically considered. How the new plan perceived the position and role of urban areas, for the purpose of rational territorial organization of the Republic of Serbia and what changes enacted to establish a coherent space in the Republic of Serbia, are some of the questions this lecture tried to answer.

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Annex 3 – Teaching Exchange Report from UB-GEF to U_Polis (Šećerov)

Teaching period – March 27th to 31st, 2023

Visiting researcher

Name: Velimir

Surname: Šećerov

Sending institution: UB-GEF

E-mail: velimir.secerov@gef.bg.ac.rs secerovv@gmail.com

Hosting institution

Name: POLIS University

Department: IDAUP Program, XXXV Cycle. Polis University

Contact person: Doriana Musaj, deputy Dean of the Faculty of Urban Planning and Urban Management

Synthesis of the visiting activities conducted (teaching modules/workshops/public-open lectures):

The teaching module was coordinated with zoom meetings and tete-a-tete meetings in Tirana in POLIS University premises on 27th and 28th of March 2023. It was agreed that the students of the IDAUP Program, XXXV Cycle are interested to participate on a lecture related to spatial planning. The lecture was carefully designed and structured to also fit the lectures of the other colleagues from the UBGEF and CEA coordinated joined module for lecturing at the POLIS University. The format of the lecture was public-open lecture with a duration of 45 minutes together with discussion and questions with the audience at the end of the lecture.

Title: Public Interest and City Planning in Serbia - Development of Belgrade on the River Banks

Abstract: The accelerated urban development and the transformation of its physical structures due to the pressure of new construction, the expansion of a settlement or the change of its former purpose requires the management of the new challenges in the control and governance of such phenomena. The article presents the short historical development of Belgrade with its peculiarities, focusing on the part on the Danube and Sava coasts, the most attractive parts of the city and the highest zone of interest. Particularly important was the period after 2000, when a new generation of plans and long-term strategic documents were prepared (Regional Spatial Plan of the City of Belgrade, Master Plan of Belgrade, etc.) and a new cycle of projects was developed, mainly related to the city core. Several capital planning measures were identified at a very short interval, but some of them have not been implemented yet. (Ada Bridge, Concrete Hall, Marina Dorcol, Port of Belgrade, Ada Huja). Since 2012, the ultimate but controversial Belgrade Waterfront project has been of great interest to the local (and national) government. The last section of the presentation will also present the role of planning documents in validating the (quasi) public interest.

Learning outcomes - the focus of the study is on getting acquainted with modern approaches to urban planning, large-scale projects and public interest. Particular attention is also paid to the instruments for the implementation of such activities, that is, whether the percentage of realization is satisfactory in relation to the planned projections.

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Annex 4 – Teaching Exchange Report from UB-GEF to U_Polis (Živanović)

Teaching period – March 27th to 31st, 2023

Visiting researcher

Name: Zora

Surname: Živanović

Sending institution: UB-GEF

E-mail: zoraz17@yahoo.com

Hosting institution

Name: POLIS University

Department: IDAUP Program, XXXV Cycle. Polis University

Contact person: Doriana Musaj, deputy Dean of the Faculty of Urban Planning and Urban Management

Synthesis of the visiting activities conducted (teaching modules/workshops/public-open lectures):

The teaching activity was organized in the framework of a combined guest lecture that U-Polis conducted within the project, for the students of the IDAUP Program. The format of the lecture was public open lecture with a duration of 90 minutes together with discussion and questions. The speaker introduced the students to spatial planning and urban system in Serbia.

Title Lecture1 - Spatial Planning in Serbia: From Yugoslavia to European Integration

Title Lecture 2 - Urban System in Serbia. The Factor in the Planning of Balanced Regional Development

Abstract Lecture1 - The aim of this lecture is to present the spatial planning system in Serbia, its basic characteristics, its development path, kinds of spatial plans at each territorial level, the contents of spatial plans and spatial planning procedures. The issue of vertical and horizontal coordination, including territorial cooperation, the existence of monitoring and implementation of plans, the coherence of planned objectives and developments in the area, the degree of representation of theoretical methodology in planning documents, the classification of the country into one of the four European planning systems, as well as other numerous problems and challenges for the future in spatial planning in Serbia are contained in this presentation.

Abstract Lecture 2 - This lecture is about basic characteristics of Serbia's urban system after World War II. There will be presented results of analysis and methods common in urban geography, notably the Rank-Size Rule and the Law of the Primate City. After that are given explanations about causes of the previous and current situation in the national settlement network, as a prerequisite for planning the future organization of the settlement network. Polarization is evident in the prominent domination of the capital city in terms of population, and this is a key feature of Serbia's urban system. The current situation is the result of an intensive process of urbanization, but also of the establishment of new administrative boundaries after the disintegration of Yugoslavia. The most suitable model is suggested for Serbia's urban system that could help overcome the extreme population concentration in Belgrade and create a basis for organizing an optimal system of centers. Special attention will be paid to Belgrade, as the capital and the largest city in Serbia, in the development of settlements and centres within its administrative area, i.e. the territory administratively named the City of Belgrade. There will be presented analysis of demographic trends, including commuting trends, and the functional and morphological changes in the settlements of the Belgrade region between 1971 and 2011.

Annex 5 – Teaching Exchange Report from POLITO to U_Polis (Lami-Todella)

Teaching period – May 15th to 19th, 2023

Visiting researcher (1)

Name: Isabella M.

Surname: Lami

Sending institution: Politecnico di Torino, Italy

E-mail: isabella.lami@polito.it

Visiting researcher (2)

Name: Elena

Surname: Todella

Sending institution: Politecnico di Torino, Italy

E-mail: elena.todella@polito.it

Hosting institution

Name: Polis University, Albania

Department: Urban Planning and Management

Curricula in which the module has been provided: “Master of Science in Urban Planning and Management” (2nd and 3rd year) and “Environmental Studies” (3rd year)

Contact person: Doriana Musaj, Leonora Haxhiu

Synthesis of the visiting activities conducted (teaching modules/workshops/public-open lectures).

Prof. Isabella M. Lami and Dr. Elena Todella had a teaching appointment of 30 hours, from the 15th to the 19th of May. The activities have been carried out through the course “Problem Structuring Methods for facing urban uncertainty”. The teaching exchange is framed in the WP3 “Enhance research skills & mainstream ‘WB green transition’ into teaching”, and Task 3.3, allowing scholars from partner institutions to contribute to existing courses on subjects related to just green transitions with lectures drawing on the results of the project. The teaching activities relate to methodologies for analyzing the feasibility of projects and plans and evaluating their economic and extra-economic effects through monetary or approaches, such as Problem Structuring Methods and Multi-Criteria Decision Analyses.

Title: Problem Structuring Methods for facing urban uncertainty

Abstract: MuVAM (Multi-Values Appraisal Methodology) is a methodological approach that uses a software to support decision-making processes related to complex problems, developed at Politecnico di Torino by Professor Isabella M. Lami and DEM Future company (<https://demfuture.com/progetto/muvam/>).

It enables analysis, collaborative discussion, shared solution development, and deliberation with respect to a decision problem through an interface designed to make the complexity of the components involved usable. It contributes to structuring and representing decision-making problems through a participatory mode, which can occur both in presence and remotely and possibly asynchronously, to facilitate the final deliberation, which still remains in the purely human sphere.

MuVAM consists of a multi-methodology combining the Strategic Choice Approach (SCA) (Friend and Hickling, 2005) and Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) (Saaty, 1980), through an innovative pathway, which allows the two methodologies to be combined into a single, interactive, and customizable flow based on the users and the type of case being analyzed.

The assumption is that it is not always possible to find a single uncontested representation of the problem under consideration and therefore models should be used to inform negotiations about the nature of the problem situation. In the problem representation process, stakeholders can understand and discuss the problem, engage with each other, and work to identify potential improvements. Thus, MuVAM could be used by stakeholder groups in a workshop setting, where stakeholders can share and understand different perspectives, to arrive at shared solutions.

Teaching Agenda

Monday 15th May (8.30-13.30)	
Introduction and presentation of the GreenFORCE project, the course and the agenda	30 min. (8.30-9.00)
Theoretical illustration of the multi-methodology (1): the Strategic Choice Approach (SCA) and Problem Structuring Methods (PSMs)	1 h 15 min. (9.00-10.15)
Indication about the case study and the decision problem	30 min. (10.15-10.45)
Break	15 min. (10.45-11.00)
Brief self-presentation by students and group definition	30 min. (11.00-11.30)
Analysis of the case study and initial identification of the decision-making problem (group activity, part 1, with teaching support in classroom if needed)	2 h (11.30-13.30)
Tuesday 16th May (8.30-17.30)	
Analysis of the case study and initial identification of the decision-making problem (group activity, part 2, with available teaching support through google classroom if needed)	9 h
Wednesday 17th May (8.30-17.30)	
Group discussion and presentation about the identified decision-making problem (group activity)	1 h 30 min. (8.30-10.00)
Theoretical illustration of the multi-methodology (2): the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Multi-Criteria Decision Analyses (MCDA)	1 h 15 min. (10.00-11.15)
Break	15 minutes (11.15-11.30)
Illustration of the MuVAM software and questions	1 h (11.30-12.30)
Lunch break	1 h 30 min. (12.30-14.00)
Definition of the decision areas from the list and focus (group activity)	1 h 30 min. (14.00-15.30)
Discussion around the decision areas and focus	45 min. (15.30-16.15)
Identification of the options for the case study (group activity)	1 h 15 min. (16.15-17.30)
Thursday 18th May (8.30-15.30)	
Definition of the option tree	1 h 30 min. (8.30-10.00)
Discussion on the option tree	45 min. (10.00-10.45)
Break	15 min. (10.45-11.00)
Illustration of the KPIs for comparing the alternatives	30 min. (11.00-11.30)
Comparison with the selection of KPIs provided by us (group activity + individual activity)	1 h (11.30-12.30)
Lunch break	1 h 30 min. (12.30-14.00)
Discussion on the comparisons and results	1 h (14.00-15.00)
Evaluation of the experience and feedback through a Google form survey	30 min. (15.00-15.30)

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PAV POLIS UNIVERSITY [GROUP 1]

Making the area more accessible by using different methods of transportation and improving infrastructure in a sustainable way.

Last update: 18/05/2023 10:32

Teams

PAV POLIS UNIVERSITY [GROUP 2]

SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY

Last update: 18/05/2023 10:28

Teams

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MOBILITY
GRETA SHEHU
ACCEPTED

How can we make the area more accessible?

Last comment
No data available

TRANSPORTATION METHODS
GRETA SHEHU
ACCEPTED

What other transportation methods can we use beside road transport?

Last comment
No data available

PUBLIC PARKING
GRETA SHEHU
ACCEPTED

How can we increase the number of public parking spots?

Last comment
No data available

NBS
GRETA SHEHU
ACCEPTED

How can we improve and moderate the quality of air and water pollution?

Last comment
No data available

A

B

Annex 6 – Teaching Exchange Report from POLITO to U_Polis (Caldarice-Mohabat Doost)

Teaching period – dates 22th May – 26th May, 2023

Visiting researcher (1)

Name: Ombretta

Surname: Caldarice

Sending institution: Politecnico di Torino

E-mail: ombretta.caldarice@polito.it

Visiting researcher (2)

Name: Danial

Surname: Mohabat Doost

Sending institution: Politecnico di Torino

E-mail: danial.mohabat@polito.it

Hosting institution

Name: Universiteti Polis

Department: Department of Environment, Faculty of Planning, Environment and Urban Management

Curricula in which the module has been provided: Bachelor in Environmental Studies

Contact person: Dr. Gentian Hykaj (Department Supervisor) and Dr. Emanuela Toto

Synthesis of the visiting activities conducted

The teaching exchange on “Resilience and Climate Change” aimed to give the students a comprehensive framework about the EU Green Transition, understating how resilience-oriented policies can have a leading role in overcoming climate change and environmental degradation, fostering climate neutrality by 2050, boosting the economy through green technology, creating sustainable industry and transport, and cutting pollution. The teaching exchange has been organised in five lectures on resilience, climate change, and just green transition in international science, policy and practice, and a workshop on measuring territorial vulnerabilities to supporting just green transition in Tirana.

Generally, the learning outcomes have been the following:

- Develop knowledge of resilience
- Expand awareness on policies and tools that support a just green transition in tackling global threats
- Investigate urban resilience practices with case studies from cities worldwide
- Conduct a preliminary measurement of territorial vulnerabilities in Tirana Prefecture
- Analyse the current and future urban trends at the local level
- Forecast future resilient scenarios for just green transition

Lecture 1 The fundamental of resilience in global challenges science

Abstract: Lecture 1 aimed to **frame the concept of resilience**, from its roots in ecology to resilience thinking in spatial planning. The term resilience stems from the Latin "resilio", meaning to spring back. It is an umbrella concept because of its great attractiveness to solve urban challenges, a semantic utopia that should help design multidisciplinary knowledge networks to innovate planning and practices. Resilience has been developed **with**

different meanings for over forty years within engineering, ecology, biology, social psychology, and regional economics.

In the academic literature, it is possible to recognise **three scholars' definitions of the concept of resilience**: (i) engineering resilience; (ii) ecological resilience; and (iii) socio-ecological resilience. In the planning theory, the turning point of resilience in spatial planning is the seminal special issue edited by Simin Davoudi and Libby Porter on Planning Theory & Practice published in 2012. It is the first attempt to adapt the resilience concept to spatial planning, proposing the so-called **evolutionary resilience** defined as the ability of a territorial system to improve its adaptive capacity intending to evolve all its material and immaterial components toward a new territorial system's organisation after unexpected shocks and disturbances. In the last twenty years, a flourishing theoretical debate on resilience as a new way to think about spatial planning has been developed. What emerged from the planning practice is that resilience has commonly been framed as the desired end of the planning process to frame prevention, study solutions, and realise interventions against shocks and events. In this perspective, resilience is simply a "system trait or condition" or "outcome". **To welcome the just green transition - here defined as the ability of cities to stay functional by coping, absorbing, recovering and adapting – resilience should be set as a process to select value goals and the needed action during the planning process.**

Key takeaway messages:

- *Resilience is a turbulent world;*
- *Resilience is not "readably used";*
- *Resilience is not a top-down decision;*
- *Resilience has to be defined as a process;*
- *Resilience is a requirement for sustainability.*

Lecture 2

Urban resilience, climate change, and just green transition in international policies

Abstract Lecture 2 aimed to **frame international policies related to urban resilience, climate change, and just green transition**. The starting point is that we are facing worldwide different types of challenges: (i) urbanization challenges (as cities consume 75% of natural resources and 80% of energy supply and produce 80% of carbon emissions and 50% of global waste); (ii) development challenges, related to poverty, sprawl, inequality, pollution, security, depletion/access of resources; and (iii) climate challenges, caused by direct threat slow/rapid on-setting risk. In this scenario, **local governments play a strategic role** in addressing climate change because of their responsibility in plans and regulations, which can influence innovative mitigation and adaptation solutions. **In 2009 United Nations questioned if "resilience is the solution"**. From that moment on, the international policy momentum began to think about mitigation and adaptation to climate change from a resilience perspective (the Sustainable Development Goals; the Sendai Framework; the New Urban Agenda; the Paris Agreement). **The Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) represent the heart of the Paris Agreement**. Parties shall prepare, communicate and maintain successive NDCs with increasing ambition. The NDCs combine the focus on mitigation, by defining clear goals and means to reduce GHG emissions, and adaptation, by communicating needs, plans and actions related to adaptation to climate change. **Albania submitted in October 2021 NDCs**, highlighting that Albania has developed and implemented a large number of adaptation-related policies, strategies, plans, programmes, projects and actions to enhance adaptive capacity, strengthen resilience and reduce vulnerability to climate change, to contribute to sustainable development and ensure an adequate adaptation response to high temperature.

At the European level, the lecture proposed a tentative timeline of the EU strategies. The starting point is the **EU Green Deal (2019)**. The new growth strategy aims to transform the EU into a fair and prosperous society with a

modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy with no net emissions of greenhouse gases in 2050, and economic growth is decoupled from resource use. At the same time, this transition must be just and inclusive.

Key takeaway messages:

- *Climate adaptation responses at the urban level should be strengthened by supporting a concrete identification of urban adaptation responses across all adaptation sectors;*
- *Multi-level governance is a fundamental enabling condition for climate action at the local level. It requires vertical integration of national policies with local action, and horizontal integration, enhancing collaboration between local administration, stakeholders and civil society.*

Lecture 3

Urban resilience practices with case studies from cities worldwide

Abstract Lecture 3 aimed to present **case studies worldwide** that approached urban resilience to face contemporary challenges. The starting point of this lecture is that it is impossible to have a comprehensive overview of urban resilience practices worldwide because, as resilience is a place-based concept, urban projects define resilience with many approaches.

The first presented case study is **Copenhagen**. During the past 30 years, Copenhagen has undergone tremendous development. From a city with a terrible economy and declining population, it has been transformed into a vibrant city with a growing population, a strong economy, an international reputation for implementing green solutions, and one of the world's most liveable cities. After the catastrophic 2011 cloudburst, the City approved the **2012 Cloudburst Management Plan** to address the challenge of floodwater holistically. After, the City approved the **2015 Adaptation Plan**, fostering a Copenhagen carbon neutral by 2025.

The second case study is **Barcelona**, which in 2015 approved the **Strategy "Superilla"**. The Superblock programme is taking a step ahead and becoming the street transformation model for the entire City, aiming to reclaim the space currently occupied by private vehicles for citizens. The goal is to create a healthy, greener, fairer, and safer public space promoting social relations and the local economy.

The third case study is **London**, which in 2015 approved the **London 2050 Environmental Strategy** to take a range of immediate actions to improve the environment now, setting London on the path to creating a better future and envisaging making London Greener and a National City Park. T

he fourth case study is **Bologna**, which approved the **2015 Adaptation Plan** to contrast urban heat islands, extreme meteorological events, and drought. The **2021 Bologna land use plan** mainstreamed resilience and adaptation to climate change to reinforce urban regeneration, develop ecological networks, avoid territorial risks and support the green transition. Lastly, the **New York Green Infrastructure Plan** and the **Dallas Climate Plan** have been presented.

Key takeaway messages:

- *It is not possible to have a comprehensive overview of urban resilience initiatives as they are very different;*
- *Urban projects define resilience with many approaches;*
- *Contrasting the effect of climate change and managing uncontrolled urbanisation are the top challenges;*
- *Assuming a planning perspective, it would be better to investigate resilient solutions in planning processes.*

Lecture 4

Preliminary knowledge on measuring territorial vulnerabilities for just green transition

Abstract Lecture 4 presented an **overview of measuring and assessing resilience**. Efforts to apply resilience in the global challenge science have stimulated interest in assessing and measuring resilience and given rise to an array of approaches, i.e. qualitative and quantitative methods, participatory assessments, statistical analyses, and modelling and metrics. **Many methods to measure and assess resilience have proliferated in recent years**. They can be classified differently (levels, actors, approaches, outputs). In order to create a fruitful connection between resilience definition in the planning process and the measuring and assessing of resilience, the lecture presented three methods that interpret resilience as a condition, an outcome, and a process. Specifically: (i) the method "**Indicators for Resilient Cities**" by OECD interpreted resilience as a condition; (ii) the method "**Making Cities Resilient 2030**" by UNDRR interpreted resilience as a performance; and (iii) the method "**City Resilience Index (CRI)**" by the Rockefeller Foundation interpreted resilience as a performance.

The **R3C methodology** - that the students utilized during the workshop to measure territorial vulnerabilities in Tirana with particular reference to green transition – **interpreted resilience as a process**. It follows three principles:

1. Building the **analysis of territorial vulnerabilities** as a tool of technical knowledge for decision-making, aimed at defining strategies, actions, and preparedness projects towards transformative resilience;
2. Promote the **multiscale and intersectoral dimension of resilience**, integrating adaptation objectives into the territorial governance;
3. Support the **construction of a set of land maintenance actions** that implement adaptation in a social learning perspective for the system's resilience.

Key takeaway messages:

- *It is necessary to shift from measuring resilience as a city's condition or performance to a process that improves the competence of urban systems to react to urban challenges;*
- *It is necessary to use resilience-oriented indicators instead of existing indicators used for developing an urban resilience measurement tool;*
- *It is necessary to consider the interaction between different urban system components, although they use indicators that cover multiple dimensions of urban resilience.*

WORKSHOP

From territorial vulnerabilities to just green transition

Abstract During the workshop, theoretical and practical knowledge of GIS and their role in measuring territorial vulnerabilities were provided to the students. An **empirical case focusing on the city of Tirana** was employed, where the **students utilized the R3C methodology to measure territorial vulnerabilities and learned how to apply the methodology in Tirana with particular reference to green transition**.

The first part of the workshop focused on the **selection, calculation, and visualization of sensitivity and pressure indicators** which are used to measure territorial vulnerabilities. These indicators referred to different components such as environment, infrastructure, services, and economy. The students were guided through the process of collecting data and calculating these indicators using GIS tools.

After understanding how to calculate sensitivity and pressure indicators, the workshop emphasized the significance of their interaction in measuring vulnerabilities. The students learned that vulnerability is determined by the interplay between these two categories of indicators. By analysing their combined effects, the students gained insights into the relative impact of these indicators. In this respect the students were divided into two groups for a role-playing exercise. **Each group was tasked with filling out the R3C matrix using sensitivity and pressure indicators**. Upon completing the exercise, the two groups presented their respective

matrixes and identified differences in the outcomes highlighting the variations in indicator weights assigned by each group and discussed the underlying reasons for these differences.

In the next phase, the **students learned how to combine the weighted indicators using map overlay techniques, with the guidance of the tutors.** This process enabled the creation of a synthesis maps, representing the spatial distribution of territorial vulnerabilities in Tirana. The **synthesis map provided valuable insights into areas that require focused attention and intervention for enhancing resilience.** In addition, at the end, the students discussed the differences in the vulnerability maps that they created. In other words, despite calculating and using the same indicators of pressures and sensitivities, different indicator weights assigned by the two groups led to different results, so the students learned how different points of view can create different outcomes. In a broader sense, they noticed through a practical exercise why stakeholder engagement, collaborative discussions, and considering different voices from different groups are helpful for measuring territorial vulnerabilities. **This final point enabled them to have a deeper understanding of the justice dimension of the green transition.**

Teaching Agenda

Lecture Title	Duration
Day 1 May, 22 The fundamentals of resilience in global challenges science (Ombretta Caldarice)	2 hours
Day 1 May, 22 Urban resilience, climate change, and just green transition in international policies (Ombretta Caldarice)	2 hours
Day 2 May, 23 Urban resilience practices with case studies from cities worldwide (Ombretta Caldarice)	3 hours
Day 2 May, 23 Preliminary knowledge on measuring territorial vulnerabilities for just green transition (Ombretta Caldarice)	3 hours
Day 3 May, 24 The Geographic Information Systems (GIS) in resilience measurement (Danial Mohabat Doost)	2 hours
Day 3 May, 24 Group activities. Stakeholders' participation for weighting vulnerability indicators (Danial Mohabat Doost)	2 hours
Day 4 May, 25 Group activities. Analysis of the urban trends and drivers at the local level (Danial Mohabat Doost)	2 hours
Day 4 May, 25 Group activities. Forecast of future resilient scenarios for just green transition (Danial Mohabat Doost)	2 hours
Day 5 May, 26 Group presentation. From territorial vulnerabilities to just green transition (Danial Mohabat Doost & Ombretta Caldarice)	2 hours
Total	20 hours

Day 1 | May, 22

Ombretta Calderice is presenting

teaching exchange on
Resilience and Climate Change

Ombretta Calderice & Danial Mohabat Doost
Politecnico di Torino
Interuniversity Department of Regional and Urban Studies and Planning
Responsible Risk Resilience Centre - R3C

Universiteti Polis Tirana | 22-26 May 2023

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10:30 AM | nzp-cciw-ehh

Day 2 | May, 23

Ombretta Calderice is presenting

Tirana in action

Funded by the European Union

City of Tirana
Climate change project

- Case study areas
- Good practice examples

Danial Mohabat Doost

10:30 AM | nzp-cciw-ehh

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Day 3 | May, 24

Daniel Mohabat Doost is presenting

The main window displays a Google Sheet titled "R3C_Matrix-exercise_Polito_Polis". The sheet is organized into two columns: "indicator of sensitivity" and "indicator of pressure".

	B	C	D	E	F	G
1		indicator of pressure				
2	indicator of sensitivity	dynamic of population density (2011-2001)	dynamic of built up area density (2017-2022)	spatiality of economic aids		
3	permeable area = permeable area/total area					
4	Accessibility=road density/inhabitants					
5	Availability of educational services= schools/inhabitants					
6	Availability of health care services= healthcare facilities/inhabitants					
7	Economic productivity = business for 1000 inhabitants					

Video thumbnails on the right show Emanuela Toto and Daniel Mohabat Doost.

Day 4 | May, 25

Daniel Mohabat Doost is presenting

The main window displays a QGIS map of a geographical area with a black outline. The interface includes a toolbar at the top and a layer list on the left. The map shows terrain, roads, and water bodies.

Video thumbnails on the right show Emanuela Toto and Daniel Mohabat Doost. The bottom status bar indicates the time is 1:35 PM and the user ID is nzp-cciw-ehh.

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Day 5 | May, 26

Ombretta Caldarice is presenting

Green FORCE

Vulnerability index (Group 1)

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10:30 AM | nzp-cciw-ehh

Video call interface showing three participants in a vertical stack on the right side.

Day 5 | May, 26

Ombretta Caldarice is presenting

Emanuela Toto

10:30 AM | nzp-cciw-ehh

Video call interface showing three participants in a vertical stack on the right side.

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Annex 7 – Teaching Exchange UB-GEF to POLITO - Agenda of the activities

06/11/2023 – 10/11/2023

Valentino Castel, Turin, Italy

Teaching Staff Exchange

Velimir Šećerov, PhD is a Full Professor at the Department for Spatial Planning at the Faculty of Geography, University of Belgrade (UB-GEF). Dean of the Faculty from 2021.

Marija Jeftić, PhD is an Associate Professor at the Department for Spatial Planning at the Faculty of Geography, University of Belgrade (UB-GEF).

Zora Živanović is an Associate Professor of Introduction to spatial planning in the Faculty of geography, University of Belgrade. She received her PhD degree from the Faculty of geography, University of Belgrade in 2012

Day1 – Monday 6/11

Visit Tour to Valentino Castel / 15:00 CET

Objective: Meeting with our venue and team of professors that will support the teaching activities

Day2 – Tuesday 07/11/2023

Module : Planning theory and comparative planning studies (prof. Giancarlo Cotella)

The course provides students with (i) a theoretical standpoint on the nature of spatial governance and planning systems and how they change and evolve through time; (ii) a critical comparison of selected spatial governance and planning systems in Europe and beyond and (iii) an informed perspective of the institutional and operational influence of transnational organizations over domestic contexts, with particular attention for the European Union.

When: 8:30 – 13:00 / Where: 8V, Valentino Castel

Presentation - Spatial Planning in Serbia: From Yugoslavia to European Integration, Prof. Zora Zivanovic

Module - Seminario Introduttivo “Resilienza e Patrimonio” [Resilience and Cultural Heritage] (Prof. Ombretta Caldarice, Prof. Benedetta Giudice, Prof. Michela Benente)

The introductory seminar “Resilience and Heritage” is part of the master's degree programmes in Architecture of the Politecnico di Torino. The seminar supports students in dealing with emerging issues related to the resilience of cultural heritage and acquiring specific skills to design resilience strategies. Based on the debate with the local actors, the seminar assumes a territorial perspective to envisage future scenarios and to define strengths and weaknesses to enhance the resilience of cultural heritage.

When: 11:30 – 15:30 / Where: Lingotto – room 207

Seminar Programme

- Introduction to the seminar, Prof. Ombretta Caldarice
- Novi Beograd (New Belgrade) - From Grey Dormitories to the Modern City, Prof. Velimir Šećerov
- Public Interest and City Planning in Serbia - Development of Belgrade on the River Banks, Prof. Velimir Šećerov

Discussants: Prof. Bragaglia Francesca, Prof. Benedetta Giudice; Prof. Michela Benente and Prof. Irene Ruiz Bazan

Module - Fattibilità economica di piani e progetti (prof. Isabella Maria Lami)

The course is to provide students with a knowledge of the methods of investigation relating to the needs of users and the limits imposed by economic factors for the development of sustainable and feasible architectural projects. In particular, the aim is to analyse the entire implementation process of an adaptive reuse operation, from the phase of identification of the different uses, to the evaluation of costs and revenues for the realisation and management of the intervention; deepening the theoretical and methodological aspects related to the tools that can be used in the different phases. At the end of the course the student will have developed the ability to identify the key elements of the real estate market in order to develop a quality architectural project able to respond to the challenges of today's society.

When: 13:00 – 14:30 / Where: Via Morgari – room 7VM

Presentation - Resilient Belgrade: Spatial Planning in the Light of Climate Change, Prof Marija Jeftić

Day3 – Wednesday 08/11/2023

Seminar “Functional Areas and Urban/regional development: what nexus”

The seminar will delve into the significance of functional areas in addressing the myriad challenges that territories have encountered over the past three decades. While not a new concept, functional area is increasingly gaining prominence as an approach to define new spatial configurations and territorial alliances based on functional factors, including economic, social, and institutional interrelations.

When: 15:00 - 17:00 / Where: Sala Vigliano, Valentino Castel

Presentations:

- Intro: Functional Areas: what do they stand for? (Prof. Erblin Berisha)
- Lecture 1- Functional urban areas (FUA) as the instrument of polycentric spatial development of the Republic of Serbia (Prof. Marija Jeftić)
- Lecture 2 Urban System in Serbia—The Factor in the Planning of Balanced Regional Development (Prof. Zora Zivanovic)

Discussant: Prof. Giancarlo Cotella, Prof. Loris Servillo

Formal Dinner –20:00 at Cibo Cointainer, [Corso Guglielmo Marconi, 33](#), Turin

Day4 – Thursday 09/11/2023

Institutional Twinning Meeting—sharing of research experiences and interests

In this meeting, representatives from the DIST department and UB-GEF will discuss the structure of each institution, share details about their main research projects, and explore potential areas of research interest. Participants will also have the opportunity to discuss potential cooperation initiatives.

Where: 10:00-12:00 / Where: OGR – Meeting Room

Discussant: Giancarlo Cotella, Isabella Maria Lami (tdc), Elena Todella, Grazia Brunetta (tbc), Ombretta Caldarice, Danial Doost, Magda Bolzoni (Department resp., on Internationalisation, tbc), Elisabetta Vitale Brovarone (Department resp., on Research, tbc).

Day5 – Friday

Informal meetings

Annex 8 – Teaching Exchange Report from UB-GEF to POLITO (Jeftić)

Teaching period – 5-10th of November 2023

Visiting researcher

Name: Marija

Surname: Jeftić

Sending institution: University of Belgrade, Faculty of Geography

E-mail: marija.jeftic@gef.bg.ac.rs

Hosting institution

Name: Politecnico di Torino, Italy

Department: Spatial planning

Curricula in which the module has been provided:

1. Economic feasibility of plans and projects (Contact person: Prof. Isabella Maria Lami)
2. Seminar "Functional Areas and Urban/regional development: what nexus" (Contact persons: prof. Erblin Berisha, prof. Giancarlo Cotella)

Synthesis of the visiting activities conducted (teaching modules/workshops/public-open lectures.):

The Polito University conducted a combined guest lectures within Horizon frame, on 7th and 8th of November 2023, for the students of the bachelor and master Spatial planning programme. The lectures were carefully designed and structured to also fit the lectures of the other colleagues from UB-GEF. The format of the lectures was public open lectures with a duration of one and a half hour per lecture together with discussion and questions with the audience at the end of the lectures. The speaker – prof. Marija Jeftić, introduced the students to resilient Belgrade and functional regionalization, and elaborated on the topics: resilience, The City Resilience Framework, Belgrade Strategy of Urban Resilience, model of FUA, spatial planning instruments, Current Strategies, Plans and Development Frameworks.

Please for each activity provide us with the following information:

<p>(1) Title: Functional urban areas (FUA) as the instrument of polycentric spatial development of the Republic of Serbia</p>
<p>Abstract: In the light of making a new Spatial plan of the Republic of Serbia 2021-2035 (SPRS), the current state and prospects of spatial development of the functional urban areas in Serbia were elaborated. With reference to previous SPRS and implementation programs, the importance of FUA in the interregional and intraregional integration of Serbia and its environment was critically considered. How the new plan perceived the position and role of urban areas, for the purpose of rational territorial organization of the Republic of Serbia and what changes enacted to establish a coherent space in the Republic of Serbia, are some of the questions this lecture tried to answer.</p>
<p>(2) Title: Resilient Belgrade: Spatial Planning in the Light of Climate Change</p>
<p>Abstract: Concept of resilience was explained in general and specifically for the City of Belgrade and its "threshold" of vulnerability, to which he can face the side effects of climate change. The lecture covered the topics from Resilience Timeline to Belgrade Regional Context (People and Economy, Culture, Arts and Sciences, Infrastructure, Climate and the Urban Environment, Governance and Budget Management, Designing an Innovative Engagement Process, Primary Shocks and Stresses, Assets and Risks). The concept of urban governance on the level of FUA, along with supporting segments, was proposed as the model for future planning of resistant Belgrade agglomeration.</p>

Teaching Agenda

Lecture Title	Duration (in hours)
Lecture 1 Functional urban areas (FUA) as the instrument of polycentric spatial development of the Republic of Serbia	1,5h
Lecture 2 Resilient Belgrade: Spatial Planning in the Light of Climate Change	1,5h

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Annex 9 – Teaching Exchange Report from UB-GEF to POLITO (Secerov)

Teaching period – 5-10th of November 2023

Visiting researcher

Name: Velimir

Surname: Šećerov

Sending institution: University of Belgrade, Faculty of Geography

E-mail: velimir.secerov@gef.bg.ac.rs

Hosting institution

Name: Politecnico di Torino, Italy

Department: Spatial planning

Curricula in which the module has been provided:

3. PUBLIC INTEREST AND CITY PLANNING IN SERBIA - DEVELOPMENT OF BELGRADE ON THE RIVER BANKS (Contact person: Prof. Ombretta Caldarice)
4. NOVI BEOGRAD (NEW BELGRADE) - From Grey Dormitories to the Modern City (Contact persons: Prof. Ombretta Caldarice)

Synthesis of the visiting activities conducted (teaching modules/workshops/public-open lectures..):

The teaching modules for the students of the bachelor and master level Architecture – Urban Planning programme were coordinated with meetings and discussions in POLITO on 7th and 8th of November 2023. The lecture was carefully designed and structured to also fit the lectures of the other colleagues from the UBGEF. The format of the lecture was public-open lecture with duration of 90 minutes together with discussion and questions with the audience at the end of the lecture.

Title

PUBLIC INTEREST AND CITY PLANNING IN SERBIA - DEVELOPMENT OF BELGRADE ON THE RIVER BANKS

Abstract of teaching activities

The accelerated urban development and the transformation of its physical structures due to the pressure of new construction, the expansion of a settlement or the change of its former purpose requires the management of the new challenges in the control and governance of such phenomena. The article presents the short historical development of Belgrade with its peculiarities, focusing on the part on the Danube and Sava coasts, the most attractive parts of the city and the highest zone of interest. Particularly important was the period after 2000, when a new generation of plans and long-term strategic documents were prepared (Regional Spatial Plan of the City of Belgrade, Master Plan of Belgrade, etc.) and a new cycle of projects was developed, mainly related to the city core. Several capital planning measures were identified at a very short interval, but some of them have not been implemented yet. (Ada Bridge, Concrete Hall, Marina Dorcol, Port of Belgrade, Ada Huja). Since 2012, the ultimate but controversial Belgrade Waterfront project has been of great interest to the local (and national) government. The last section of the presentation will also present the role of planning documents in validating the (quasi) public interest.

Learning outcomes - the focus of the study is on getting acquainted with modern approaches to urban planning, large-scale projects and public interest. Particular attention is also paid to the instruments for the implementation of such activities, that is, whether the percentage of realization is satisfactory in relation to the planned projections.

Title: NOVI BEOGRAD (NEW BELGRADE) - From Grey Dormitories to the Modern City

Abstract: The turbulent history of the development of the city of Belgrade in the 20th century is particularly interesting and visible on the left banks of its rivers (Danube and Sava). After the First World War and the merging of the northern parts of today's Belgrade, first the planning and then the construction expansion related to these areas began. In the early 60s of the last centuries, the construction of New Belgrade began, dominantly in the spirit of Corbusier's urban matrices and buildings characteristics of the epoch and social order of that time. A mixture of greenery, a well-designed traffic matrix, high-rise buildings and a large percentage of free surfaces, at the beginning there are dormitories of partially oriented populated social structures. After beginning of the 21st century, this area experienced a transformation, to such an extent that it became today an extremely acceptable place for living, business and other activities. Land unencumbered by disputes from the period of nationalization (after WWII) is attractive for building and a magnet for investments. The price per square meter of an apartment is on par with the most elite parts of the old city, the habits and structure of the population are changing, the most elite events are being organized, and the equipping with modern infrastructure continues. The subject of this paper is a brief presentation of the transformation of New Belgrade and pointing out the most interesting steps in this process.

Annex 10 – Teaching Exchange Report from UB-GEF to POLITO (Zivanovic)

Teaching period – 5-10th of November 2023

Visiting researcher

Name: Zora

Surname: Živanović

Sending institution: University of Belgrade, Faculty of Geography

E-mail: zoraz17@yahoo.com

Hosting institution

Name: Politecnico di Torino, Italy

Department: DIST - Interuniversity Department of Regional and Urban Studies and Planning

Curricula in which the module has been provided:

1. Planning theory and comparative planning studies (prof. Giancarlo Cotella)
2. Seminar "Functional Areas and Urban/regional development: what nexus" (Contact persons: prof. Erblin Berisha, prof. Giancarlo Cotella)

Synthesis of the visiting activities conducted (teaching modules/workshops/public-open lectures.):

The Department: DIST - Interuniversity Department of Regional and Urban Studies and Planning conducted a combined guest lectures within Horizon frame, on 7th and 8th of November 2023, for the students of the bachelor and master programme. The lectures were carefully designed and structured to also fit the lectures of the other colleagues from UB-GEF. The format of the lectures was public open lectures with a duration of one and a half hour per lecture together with discussion and questions with the audience at the end of the lectures. The speaker – prof. Zora Živanović introduced the students to Spatial Planning in Serbia: From Yugoslavia to European Integration and to Urban System in Serbia—The Factor in the Planning of Balanced Regional Development

Title: Spatial Planning in Serbia: From Yugoslavia to European Integration

Abstract: The aim of this lecture is to present the spatial planning system in Serbia, its basic characteristics, its development path, kinds of spatial plans at each territorial level, the contents of spatial plans and spatial planning procedures. The issue of vertical and horizontal coordination, including territorial cooperation, the existence of monitoring and implementation of plans, the coherence of planned objectives and developments in the area, the degree of representation of theoretical methodology in planning documents, the classification of the country into one of the four European planning systems, as well as other numerous problems and challenges for the future in spatial planning in Serbia are contained in this presentation.

Title: Urban System in Serbia—The Factor in the Planning of Balanced Regional Development

Abstract: This lecture is about basic characteristics of Serbia's urban system after World War II. There will be presented results of analysis and methods common in urban geography, notably the Rank-Size Rule and the Law of the Primate City. After that are given explanations about causes of the previous and current situation in the national settlement network, as a prerequisite for planning the future organization of the settlement network. Polarization is evident in the prominent domination of the capital city in terms of population, and this is a key feature of Serbia's urban system. The current situation is the result of an intensive process of urbanization, but also of the establishment of new administrative boundaries after the disintegration of Yugoslavia. The most suitable model is suggested for Serbia's urban system that could help overcome the extreme population concentration in Belgrade and create a basis for organizing an optimal system of centers. Special attention will be paid to Belgrade, as the capital and the largest city in Serbia, in the development of settlements and centres within its administrative area, i.e. the territory administratively named the City of Belgrade. There will be presented analysis of demographic trends, including commuting trends, and the functional and morphological changes in the settlements of the Belgrade region between 1971 and 2011.

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Annex 11 – Secondments agenda: For coordinating activities between Nordregio – Co-PLAN

Secondment's period: 24 March - 1 April 2023

24 March 2023, Friday

Activities to take place in Co-PLAN offices (Polis University or Co-PLAN, RDPA office in Tirana)

- 9:00 – 13:00 Meeting with Co-PLAN Vice Executive Director, reviewing the expectations and agenda
Alberto Giacometti, Anila Bejko
- 14.00 – 17.00 Supporting the preparation of the RAB meeting, working for the presentation on the Conceptualization of the JGT in WB, *Alberto Giacometti, Anila Bejko, Fiona Imami*

27 March 2023, Monday

Activities to take place in Co-PLAN offices (Polis University)

- 9.30 – 11.30 Discussion on the Policy Briefs (GreenFORCE T2.4), topics and focus
Alberto, Anila, Kejt, Fiona, Rodi, Merita, Aida
- 11.30 – 13.00 Work on the preparation of the WSH with young researchers / professionals
Alberto, Elvis, Anila
- 14.00 – 17.00 Brainstorming and discussion on potential proposals
Alberto, Marjan, Kejt, Rodi, Merita, Anila, Aida, Ogerta

28 March 2023, Tuesday

Activities to take place in Tirana, Rogner Hotel

- 9.00 – 15.30 National Forum on Climate Change in Albania, participation and input
Alberto, Marjan, Rodi, Dritan, Anila, Erni

29 March 2023, Wednesday

Activities to take place in Co-PLAN offices (Polis University)

- 9.00 – 12.00 Moderate and facilitate an internal discussion in Co-PLAN with researchers on bridging research - policy gap (Anila/Fiona to facilitate)
Participants: Elvis Ndreka, Erni Kocani, Rea Muka, Enkela Poro, Besmir Geziqi, Rudina Pasholli, Imeld Sokoli, Sara Korreshi.
- 14.00 – 17.00 Work on Policy Brief No.1 - structure and input
Alberto, Anila, Fiona

30 March 2023, Thursday

Activities to take place in Co-PLAN offices (Polis University)

- 9.00 – 10.30 Preparing for the PMB meeting
- 11.00 – 13.00 GreenFORCE 9th PMB meeting
All partners
- 14.00 – 17.00 Discussion and brainstorming on Macro-regional Networks
Alberto, Marjan, Anila, Kejt, Rodion, Elona, Dritan

31 March 2023, Friday

Activities to take place in Tirana and Durres

- 9.00 – 18.30 Site visits with RAB members and meetings with stakeholders

1 April 2023, Saturday

Activities to take place in Tirana, Xheko Hotel

- 9.00 – 15.30 RAB meeting in Tirana
All partners and RAB members

